

that separated out on cooling was filtered, washed several times with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol-water (Tables 1 and 2).

TABLE 2—BIS[*N*-ARYL-*N'*-ACETYLUREIDO]-*O*-POLY-METHYLENE BISXANTHATES (2)^a

Compd. no.	R	Molecular formula	M.p. °C
n=2			
15.	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₈ S ₄	98-100
16.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₈ S ₄	111
17.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₈ S ₄	114
18.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₈ S ₄	80-83
19.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₈ S ₄	115-116
20. ^b	<i>p</i> -Br	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ Br ₂ N ₄ O ₈ S ₄	120
21.	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ Cl ₂ N ₄ O ₈ S ₄	115
n=3			
22.	H	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₆	140-42
23.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₆	195-98
24. ^b	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₆	189-90
25.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₆	205
26.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	C ₃₀ H ₂₈ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₆	160-61
27.	<i>p</i> -Br	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ Br ₂ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₆	176-77
28.	<i>p</i> -Cl	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ Cl ₂ N ₆ O ₁₂ S ₆	230-31

^aAll the compounds were obtained in 60-70% yield, and they gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

^b $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) Compd. 20, 3210 (NH), 1700 (NHCONH), 1600, 1492 (C=C, aromatic), 1405 (CH₂CO), 1240 (O-N, stretch), 1130 (C=S) and 835 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring) cm⁻¹; Compd. 24, 3200 (NH), 1700 (NHCONH), 1600, 1520 (C=C, aromatic), 1415 (CH₂CO), 1245 (O-N, stretch), 1180 (O=S) and 810 (1,4-disubstituted benzene ring) cm⁻¹.

Screening for antifungal activity: All these *N*-aryl-*N'*-acetylureido-*O*-alkylxanthates (1) and bis[*N*-aryl-*N'*-acetylureido]-*O*-polymethylene bisxanthates (2) were screened for their antifungal activity against *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Alternaria alternata* as the test fungi by paper-disc plate method of Thornberry⁸ at concentrations 2.0 and 0.2% (w/v). Standard PDA medium was used. Filter paper discs of diameter 12 mm were used and the diameter of zones of inhibition formed around each disc after incubating for a period of 48 h at 25-28° were recorded. Results were compared with the reference fungicide, Thiram 75W. The compounds 1, 3, 4, 5, 9, 15, 18, 20, 21, 22, 26 and 27 were found to possess significant antifungal activity against all the test fungi.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P.C.J.) is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

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Synthesis of Substituted Acetamides as Potential Antibacterial and Antiviral Agents

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Manuscript received 30 April 1984, accepted 18 January 1985

1,2,4-TRIAZENES are associated with diverse pharmacological activities such as antimicrobial^{1,2}, antiviral³, antiinflammatory⁴, antimalarial⁵, insecticidal⁶ and AchE inhibitory activities⁷ and in addition, aryl ureas have also been reported to exhibit a wide spectrum of biological activities. With this view it was thought of interest to synthesise various 2-[[8-substituted-5H/CH₃-1,2,4-triazeno[5,6-b]indol-3-yl]-thio]-*N*-[[substituted phenyl]amino]-carbonyl]-acetamides (5-26) by condensing 8-substituted-5H/CH₃-1,2,4-triazeno [5,6-b]indol-3-thiol (1-4) and chloroacetylated ureas in ethanolic NaOH solution.

Scheme

Experimental

The structures of all the compounds were checked by ir recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 infracord

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-[8-SUBSTITUTED-5H/CH₃-1,2,4-TRIAZENO[5,6-b]-INDOL-3-YL-THIO]-N-[(SUBSTITUTED PHENYL)AMINO]ACETAMIDES (5-26)

Compd. no.	R	R ₁	R ₂	Molecular formula	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
						S	H	N
5	H	H	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	209	57.22 (57.14)	3.80 (3.70)	22.10 (22.22)
6	H	H	4-Cl	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	210	52.26 (52.36)	3.15 (3.39)	20.21 (20.36)
7	H	H	4-OH ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	228	58.22 (58.16)	4.12 (4.08)	21.22 (21.42)
8	H	H	3-OH ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	202	58.28 (58.16)	4.21 (4.08)	21.21 (21.42)
9	H	H	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	225	53.43 (53.43)	3.87 (3.92)	20.67 (20.58)
10	H	H	3-OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	218	53.25 (53.43)	3.79 (3.92)	20.56 (20.58)
11	Cl	H	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	199	52.21 (52.36)	3.36 (3.39)	20.26 (20.36)
12	Cl	H	4-Cl ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ SCl ₂	242	48.21 (48.21)	2.67 (2.68)	18.75 (18.79)
13	Cl	H	4-OH ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ SCl	204	53.60 (53.45)	3.56 (3.52)	16.60 (16.69)
14	Cl	H	3-OH ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ SCl	209	53.50 (53.45)	3.67 (3.52)	16.50 (16.69)
15	Cl	H	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ SCl	190	51.42 (51.52)	3.45 (3.38)	18.75 (18.98)
16	Cl	H	3-OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ SCl	218	51.45 (51.52)	3.21 (3.38)	18.77 (18.98)
17	Br	H	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ SBr	227	47.21 (47.26)	2.75 (2.84)	18.21 (18.38)
18	Br	H	4-Cl	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ SBrCl	280	43.80 (43.94)	2.64 (2.44)	17.15 (17.09)
19	Br	H	4-OH ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ SBr	228	48.70 (48.40)	3.40 (3.18)	17.65 (17.83)
20	Br	H	3-OH ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ SBr	219	48.67 (48.40)	3.25 (3.18)	17.75 (17.83)
21	Br	H	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ SBr	187	46.87 (46.81)	3.18 (3.08)	17.24 (17.24)
22	Br	H	3-OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ SBr	209	46.71 (46.81)	3.21 (3.08)	17.35 (17.24)
23	Cl	OH ₂	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ SCl	216	53.25 (53.45)	3.56 (3.51)	19.56 (19.69)
24	Cl	OH ₂	4-OH ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄ SCl	191	54.56 (54.48)	3.65 (3.85)	19.21 (19.06)
25	Cl	OH ₂	3-OH ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄ SCl	198	54.21 (54.48)	3.70 (3.85)	19.12 (19.06)
26	Cl	OH ₂	4-OCH ₃	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄ SCl	166	52.50 (52.69)	3.65 (3.72)	18.26 (18.46)

spectrometer. The pmr spectra were taken on a Varian EM 360 spectrometer using TMS as internal reference. The purity of all the compounds was checked on Silica gel-G plates using iodine vapour as visualising agents. Melting points were taken in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected (Table 1).

5-Substituted indol-2,3-diones and 5-chloro-1-methylindol-2,3-diones were prepared by the methods of Marvel and Hiers⁸, and Harley-Menson and Ingleby⁹, respectively.

8-Substituted-5H/CH₃-1,2,4-triazeno [5,6-b]-indol-3-thiol (1-4) : The compounds were synthesised by

refluxing equimolar mixture of 5-substituted-1H/CH₃-indol-2,3-diones (0.1 mol) and thiosemicarbazide (0.1 mol) and potassium carbonate (0.15 mol) in water for 8 h. The hot solution was filtered, cooled and acidified with 4N HCl to give the desired thiol.

1-Chloro-N-[(substituted phenyl)amino]-carbonyl-acetamides were obtained by the methods of Jacobs *et al.*¹¹.

2-[[8-Chloro-5H-1,2,4-triazeno[5,6-b]-indol-3-yl]-thio]-N-[(substituted phenyl)amino]carbonylacetamide (11) : 8-Chloro-5H-1,2,4-triazeno [5,6-b]-indol-

NOTES

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL AND ANTIVIRAL, SCREENING DATA

Compd. no.	Antibacterial assay*						Antiviral assay			
	<i>B. pumilus</i>	<i>B. cereus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. lutea</i>	<i>M. flavus</i>	% inhibition of SRV		% inhibition of TMV	
							<i>in vitro</i>	<i>in vivo</i>	<i>in vitro</i>	<i>in vivo</i>
5	++	++	++	+	+	+	59	40		
6	-	+	+	-	+	-	0	0		
7	+	+	+	+	-	-	41	40		
8	++	++	++	+	-	+	47	34		
9	-	+	+	+	-	-	0	0		
10	+	+	++	+	-	-	48	18		
11	++	++	+++	++	-	-	76	58		
12	++	-	++	+++	++	++	72	33		
13	++	+	++	+	+	++	56	56		
14	++	+	++	+	+	+	65	51		
15	++	+	++	-	+	+	43	17		
16	++	-	+++	-	-	-	72	58		
17	-	+	-	-	-	-	05	0		
18	+	++	++	+	-	+	57	34		
19	-	+	+	+	+	+	65	53		
20	-	-	-	+	+	-	51	46		
21	-	+	++	+	++	+	65	58		
22	+	+	++	-	-	-	50	40		
23	++	++	++	+	++	+	71	53	63	50
24	-	++	++	+	++	+	58	32	65	48
25	-	+	-	-	-	-	0	0	0	0
26	+	++	+	+	+	+	49	7	52	13

Tetracyclic hydrochloride 32 mm 30 mm 30 mm 27 mm 28 mm 26 mm

* - = No inhibition, + = 5-7 mm, ++ = 7-10 mm, +++ = 10-15 mm.

3-thiol (0.68 g, 0.003 mol) was added to a solution of sodium hydroxide (0.12 g, 0.003 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) and the reaction mixture stirred until a clear solution was obtained. To that solution 1-chloro-N-[(phenyl amino) carbonyl] acetamide (0.64 g, 0.003 mol) was added and heated under reflux on a water-bath for 5 h. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water and the solid mass thus obtained was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from alcohol (0.8 g, 68%), m.p. 199° (Found: C, 52.21; H, 3.36; N, 20.26. $C_{18}H_{19}N_3O_2S$ requires C, 52.36; H, 3.39; N, 20.36%). ν_{max} (KBr) 1720 (C=O), 3150 (NH), 1600 (C=N) and 2900 cm^{-1} (CH_2); δ (TFA) 3.9-4.1 (2H, s, CH_2) and 7.1-7.55 (8H, m, Ar-H); m/e 413($m+1$).

Biological activity:

Antibacterial assay: All the compounds have been evaluated for their *in vitro* growth inhibitory activity against the bacteria *Bacillus pumilus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Sarsena lutea* and *Mycococcus flavus* using agar diffusion technique¹². A standard 5 mm diameter sterilised filter paper disc, saturated with solution of the test compounds (10 mg ml^{-1} in DMF) was dried and placed on nutrient agar plate seeded with test organism. The seeded plate were incubated for 24 h at 37° and then the zone of inhibition were measured. All experiments were performed in triplicate. The results are recorded in Table 2.

Antiviral assay: All the compounds were also evaluated for their antiviral activity against *Sunnhep rosette virus* (SRV) on *Cyanopsis tetragonoloba* and four compounds were also evaluated

against *Tobacco mosaic virus* (TMV) maintained on systemic host *Nicotiana tabacum* Ver. N.P. 31. The procedure of Mukerjee *et al.*¹³ was followed for *in vitro* and *in vivo* antiviral-testing.

The solution of test compounds were prepared by dissolving 5 mg in 1 ml DMF and making the volume to 5 ml by distilled water. These solutions were termed "Test Solutions".

Results and Discussion

All the compounds showed marginal inhibition of the strains of bacteria used while the antiviral screening of the compounds exhibited fairly good activity. The best compound of the series were compounds 5, 8, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 18, 21, 22, 23 and 26 which inhibited the growth of both bacteria and viruses markedly. Structural variations had a direct influence on the activity of the compounds. In general, the introduction of chloro-substituent in the indoline nucleus resulted in the enhancement of the activity of the compounds. But the bromo-substituent did not have any marked influence on the activity. Introduction of a methyl group at 1-position of indoline nucleus resulted a marked fall in the activity. There was no clear structure-activity relationship when there was variation in the ureido-phenyl ring, though chloro and methyl substituents showed good results.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere thanks to the Head of Chemistry Department, Lucknow University

for providing facilities, Director, C.D.R.I. for micro and spectral analyses. One of the authors (A.K.P.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of Senior Research Fellowship.

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Synthesis of 2-(2-Acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-phenylureas-S-triazine and Study of Their Antibacterial Activity

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Manuscript received 8 June 1984, accepted 18 January 1985

UREA derivatives possess wide therapeutic activities, such as antibacterial¹, antithyroid, hypnotic and anesthetic, hypoglycemic², anthelmintic, diuretic³ and biocidal activity. Phenylacetamidourea derivatives are active anticonvulsants.

2-Acidamido group increases antipyretic activity^{4,5}. Moreover, salicylamide is more soluble than salicylic acid and has a more marked analgesic property. Salicylamide has a marked anthelmintic, antispasmodic, antipyretic and sedative action^{6,7}. Phenoxyethers of S-triazine are well-known fungicides⁸.

To study the antibacterial activity of compounds of the type 1 were synthesised by the condensation of cyanuric chloride (0.1 M) and aniline (0.1 M). The resulted product was afforded to react with salicylamide in equimolecular proportion. The compound obtained was made to condense with

various phenylureas to get the compounds of the type 1.

Experimental

Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Beckman IR-5 spectrometer equipped with NaCl prism.

4-Anilino-2,6-dichloro-S-triazine: Cyanuric chloride (0.1 mol) and aniline (0.1 mol) in dioxane or acetone were refluxed for 3 h on water-bath at pH 9.2 by adding aqueous NaOH (2%). The clear solution thus obtained was added in crushed ice and then filtered, washed with dil. HCl and crystallised from ethanol (80%), m.p. 163°.

2-(2-Acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-chloro-S-triazine⁹: Salicylamide (0.01 mol) was dissolved in acetone and NaOH solution (5%) was added dropwise until the solution appeared clear. It was added dropwise during 1.5 h to a mechanically stirred solution of 4-anilino-2,6-dichloro-S-triazine (0.01 mol) in dioxane at 35°. The temperature was gradually increased at 45° during 2 h. The pH was maintained 9.2 by the addition of aqueous NaOH. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature. It was added in crushed ice and HCl solution (2%). The compound obtained was filtered, dried and recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 241-42°.

General method for preparation of 2-(2-acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-phenylurea-S-triazine: 2-(2-Acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-chloro-S-triazine (0.01 mol) and various phenylureas (0.015 mol) in acetone or dioxane were refluxed for-3 h on water-bath keeping pH of the solution at 9.2 by adding aqueous NaOH (2%). Clear solution was added in crushed ice, filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. The yield of the compounds varied from 69 to 82%; m.p. R₁ = phenyl, 165°; o-tolyl, 185°; m-tolyl, 157°; p-tolyl, 145°; m-nitrophenyl, 114°; p-nitrophenyl, 120°; o-chlorophenyl, 160°; m-chlorophenyl, 130°; p-chlorophenyl, 192°.

Antibacterial activity: The purified product was screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method using a species of gram-positive bacteria, i.e. *S. aureus*, and a species of gram-negative bacteria, i.e. *E. coli*. Testing was carried out in ethanol solution at the concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹. The zone of inhibition of the test solutions were recorded.